

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Article

In-Silico Evaluation of Flavone Derivatives for Cardioprotective Effects: A Comparative Molecular Docking Approach

Sneha Nandeshwar*, Sapan Shah, Rida Saiyad, Nikita Gaikwad, Pooja Wankhade

Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Priyadarshini JL College of Pharmacy, Nagpur, 440016.

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 26 Mar. 2025

Keywords:

ADME, Binding energy, Cardioprotective agents, Docking, Toxicity, Flavones.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.15087478

ABSTRACT

Background: In this study, we used molecular docking to explore the binding affinity, ADME, and toxicity of flavone derivatives on several receptors associated with cardioprotective action. The binding affinity of several flavone derivatives to various receptors involved in cardioprotective action was determined. Auto Dock Vina, PyMol, Discovery Studio, AutoDock Tools, ChemSketch, Swiss ADME, and PROTOX 3.0. **Methods:** Molecular docking. **Results:** The binding results of the selected plant compounds and target proteins, namely 1o86, 7Q29, 5JMY, 4DLI, 2YCW, and 1CX2, showed that the good binding affinity and good receptor binding mode selected target. However, among all protein β 1 adrenergic receptor (ID:- 2YCW) showed lowest binding affinity with compound D10 (2-(4-tert-butylphenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one) (binding energy – 11.0 Kcal/mol), D44 (binding energy – 10.6 Kcal/mol). D39 (binding energy – 10.4 Kcal/mol), D32, D35 & D42 (binding energy – 10.2 Kcal/mol). **Conclusions:** The current study attempted to computationally find chemicals that can bind to the numerous targets of cardiovascular disease. The docking scores and interaction analysis indicate that most drugs have the ability to bind to many targets involved in cardiovascular illness. However, the β 1 adrenergic receptor has a high binding affinity. Absorption, distribution, metabolism, excretion, and toxicity, as well as toxicity prediction, revealed several chemicals that could be employed as possible candidates against cardiovascular disease.

INTRODUCTION

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) are the leading cause of death globally.¹ Approximately 10 million fatalities occur annually, and the figure

will climb to 23.6 million by 2030.² The leading cause of these deaths is ischemic heart disease (IHD), which claimed over 9 million lives in 2016. IHD remains the leading cause of death in countries of all income levels. Rates vary per

*Corresponding Author: Sneha Nandeshwar

Address: Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Priyadarshini JL College of Pharmacy, Nagpur, 440016.

Email : snehanadeshwar867@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

country and are declining in the majority of them, indicating a lot of potential for growth. Future progress may be hampered by rising hypertension in some developing countries, as well as global obesity rates.³ IHD has a greater death rate than other CVDs, such as stroke, hypertension, and other cardiovascular illnesses. People who follow a high saturated fatty acid, high dietary energy density, and high sodium diet are substantially more likely to develop coronary heart disease than those who do not. Cardiovascular disorders (CVDs), which include coronary heart disease (CHD), cerebrovascular disease or accident (CVA), peripheral arterial disease, and rheumatic disease, are recognized as the leading cause of death worldwide. Rising trends in CVD prevalence and deaths, particularly CHD, have focused global attention on disease prevention and control.⁴ Low-middle-income countries, such as Pakistan, India, Bangladesh, Nepal, and Sri Lanka, have a higher risk of coronary heart disease (CHD) than other countries.⁵ Obesity, physical inactivity, smoking, and hereditary predisposition all contribute to the development of cardiovascular problems.⁶ Flavone derivatives (2-phenylchromone) are naturally occurring heterocyclic compounds belonging to the flavonoid category⁷. They are abundant in many naturally occurring products and represent a significant group of oxygen heterocycles, which are widely distributed in the plant kingdom as secondary metabolites⁸. Flavonoids are a broad category of around 4000 polyphenolic chemicals found in plant-derived foods. The fundamental basis for systematic classification of these compounds is the saturation level and aperture of the major pyran ring, which results in the synthesis of flavones, flavanols, flavonols, isoflavones, and flavanonols⁹. Molecular docking is an important approach for understanding flavone derivatives' cardioprotective effect since it offers insight on their binding interactions with specific biological

targets¹⁰. This computational method enables researchers to predict the affinity and orientation of flavonoids when they interact with proteins crucial in cardiovascular health, allowing the identification of novel therapeutic agents. This knowledge contributes in the development of treatment methods for cardiovascular disorders by improving flavone derivatives' cardioprotective properties.¹¹ These interactions frequently entail the creation of hydrogen bonds and hydrophobic contacts, which are critical for the stability of the enzyme-ligand complex and improve the cardioprotective properties of these molecules¹². We used molecular docking methods to investigate the interaction between flavones and cardiovascular targets. As a result, we conducted an *in silico*, ADME, toxicity analysis docking investigation of cardiovascular disease targets using flavones derivatives.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Platform for molecular docking

The docking study of all the flavone derivatives selected as ligand and with target proteins was performed using AutoDock Vina software¹³.

2.2 Ligand preparation

UCSF chimera software retrieves the 3D structure of all compounds from the PubChem database¹⁰ (<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>). The Gasteiger charges and rotatable bonds were then allocated to the PDB ligands by Auto Dock Tool 1.5.6¹¹. The compound structures were evaluated for docking studies after minimizing their energy. (Table 1).

2.3 Protein preparation

Based on a review of the literature, a total of six proteins linked to various cardiovascular conditions were chosen (Table 2). The RCSB

protein data bank (<http://www.pdb.org>) provided the 3D structures of a few chosen target proteins. Co-crystallized ligands (X-ray ligands) were present in the binding site of every protein. Each protein structure's ligands were extracted from the binding site and stored in a different file. Using the docking program AutoDock Vina, automated molecular docking was carried out to determine molecular interaction and optimum geometry¹⁴.

2.4 ADMET and toxicity prediction

The absorption, distribution, metabolism, excretion, and toxicity (ADMET) screening of ligands contributes in determining their absorption properties, toxicity, and drug-like nature. Ligand compounds were saved in smiles format and specific drugs were submitted to SWISSADME. SWISSADME is a web-based tool for predicting ADME and pharmacokinetic features of molecules. The anticipated outcome includes lipophilicity, water solubility, physicochemical characteristics, pharmacokinetics, drug-likeness, medicinal chemistry, and brain or intestinal

estimated¹⁵. Toxicity classes include Category I (compounds with LD50 values ≤ 50 mg/kg), Category II (compounds with LD50 values > 50 mg/kg), and Category III (somewhat toxic) (compounds with LD50 values 500-5000 mg/kg), which are included in Category IV^{16,17}. PROTOX is a rodent oral toxicity server that predicts the LD50 value and toxicity class of the query substance¹⁸.

2.5 Drug likeness calculations

Drug scans were conducted to establish whether the compounds fitted the drug-likeness criteria. Lipinski's filters were used with Molinspiration (<http://www.molinspiration.com>) to examine drug likeness attributes such as the number of hydrogen acceptors (no more than 10), the number of hydrogen donors (no more than 5), the molecular weight (more than 500 daltons), and the partition coefficient log P (no less than 5). The smiles format for each compounds was uploaded for examination.

Table 1: Major flavone derivatives for docking studies.

Sr no.	IUPAC NAME	Molecular Formula	PubChem ID
D1	2-(3-nitrophenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₅ H ₉ NO ₄	252248
D2	2-(3-hydroxyphenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₃	229015
D3	2-(4-methylphenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₂	688829
D4	2-(4-methoxyphenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₃	77793
D5	2-(4-bromophenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₅ H ₉ BrO ₂	1686
D6	2-(4-aminophenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ NO ₂	177048
D7	2-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₃	229016
D8	2-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₃	161860
D9	2-(3-aminophenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ NO ₂	69569538
D10	2-(4-tert-butylphenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₂	776409
D11	2-(3-bromophenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₅ H ₉ BrO ₂	493373
D12	4-(4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran-2-yl) benzoic acid	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ O ₄	5272796
D13	2-[3,6-(di-propan-2-yl)4-hydroxy-phenyl]-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ O ₈	
D14	2-(3,4,5-trimethoxyphenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₅	332208
D15	6-tert-butyl-2-phenyl-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₂	91872361
D16	2-(4-chlorophenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₅ H ₉ ClO ₂	151515

D17	2-(3,4-dimethoxyphenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₄	688674
D18	2-(4-fluorophenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₅ H ₉ FO ₂	261391
D19	6-fluoro-2-phenyl-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₅ H ₉ FO ₂	261395
D20	6-chloro-2-phenyl-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₅ H ₉ ClO ₂	248021
D21	6-methyl-2-phenyl-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₂	689013
D22	5-hydroxy-2-(3,4,5-trimethoxyphenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₆	13302209
D23	2-(3,4-dimethoxyphenyl)-5-hydroxy-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₅	21721891
D24	2-(4-chlorophenyl)-5-hydroxy-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₅ H ₉ ClO ₃	15308132
D25	2-(4-iodophenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₅ H ₉ IO ₂	466287
D26	2-(2-fluorophenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₅ H ₉ FO ₂	261400
D27	2-(4-nitrophenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₅ H ₉ NO ₄	622510
D28	2-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₃	161860
D29	2-(2-methylphenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₂	776385
D30	2-(2-nitrophenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₅ H ₉ NO ₄	775978
D31	2-(2-ethylphenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₂	66553950
D32	2-[3-(propan-2-yl) phenyl]-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₂	
D33	2-(2-aminophenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ NO ₂	12481696
D34	5-hydroxy-2-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₄	165521
D35	5-hydroxy-2-(2-methylphenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₃	16060407
D36	5-hydroxy-2-(4-methoxyphenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₄	276147
D37	5-hydroxy-2-(4-nitrophenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₅ H ₉ NO ₅	11098040
D38	5-hydroxy-2-(3,4,5-trimethoxyphenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₆	13302209
D39	2-(2-ethylphenyl)-5-hydroxy-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₃	
D40	6-chloro-2-(4-methoxyphenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ ClO ₃	678256
D41	6-chloro-2-(4-nitrophenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₅ H ₈ ClNO ₄	5011227
D42	5-hydroxy-2-(4-methylphenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₃	11779973
D43	5-hydroxy-2-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₄	688660
D44	5-hydroxy-2-[3-(propan-2-yl) phenyl]-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₃	
D45	2-(4-aminophenyl)-5-hydroxy-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ NO ₃	46873260
D46	2-(4-aminophenyl)-6-chloro-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ ClNO ₂	82046480
D47	6-chloro-2-[3-(propan-2-yl) phenyl]-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ ClO ₂	
D48	2-(2-bromophenyl)-6-chloro-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₅ H ₈ BrClO ₂	688748
D49	6-chloro-2-(2-methoxyphenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ ClO ₃	930715
D50	6-chloro-2-(2-chlorophenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one	C ₁₅ H ₈ Cl ₂ O ₂	688872

Table 2: Targeted receptor proteins associated with cardiovascular disease Results

Sr no.	Target Proteins	Disease	PDB ID
--------	-----------------	---------	--------

1	Angiotensin-converting enzyme	Atherosclerosis/coronary artery diseases	1o86
2	ACE/NEP inhibitor	Atherosclerosis/coronary artery diseases	7Q29
3	MAPK	Myocardial infarction	4DLI
4	Neprilysin	Coronary artery disease	5JMY
5	β -1-adrenergic receptor	Chronic heart failure	2YCW
6	Cox-2	Myocardial infarction, pain	1CX2

Docking results

The binding results of the selected compounds and target proteins, namely 1o86, 7Q29, 5JMY, 4DLI, 2YCW, and 1CX2, revealed that the good binding affinity and receptor binding mode selected target. However, among all derivatives, D10 (2-(4-*tert*-butylphenyl)-4*H*-1-benzopyran-4-one) has the lowest binding energy with β -1-adrenergic receptor (binding energy – 11.0 Kcal/mol), D47 with ACE and neutral endopeptidase inhibitors (binding energy – 9.4 Kcal/mol), D47 with ACE

has lowest binding energy (binding energy – 9.2 Kcal/mol), for cox-2 the lowest binding energy with D47 derivative (binding energy – 10.5 Kcal/mol), D32 has lowest binding energy with receptor MAPK (binding energy – 10.4 Kcal/mol), D11 has lowest binding energy with protein neprilysin (binding energy – 9.4 Kcal/mol). All binding affinities of flavone derivatives are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Binding energy of flavone derivatives against targeted protein receptors

Derivative code	Cox-2 (1CX2)	ACE/NEP, ID – 7Q29	ACE (1o86)	β -1-adrenergic receptor ID:- 2YCW	MAPK ID:- 4DLI	Neprilysin ID:- 5JMY
D1	-9.4	-9.1	-8.4	-9.8	-8.5	-8.3
D2	-8.9	-8.8	-8.3	-9.6	-9.9	-9.0
D3	-10	-9.0	-8.3	-10.0	-8.6	-7.9
D4	-8.9	-8.5	-8.2	-9.4	-9.2	-8.0
D5	-9.1	-8.9	-8.1	-9.7	-8.7	-7.8
D6	-9.3	-8.5	-8.1	-9.6	-9.1	-7.7
D7	-9.6	-8.5	-8.0	-9.7	-9.2	-8.1
D8	-8.9	-8.5	-8.2	-9.3	-9.7	-8.9
D9	-9.0	-8.8	-8.3	-9.6	-9.6	-9.0
D10	-9.8	-8.9	-8.5	-11.0	-8.7	-8.3
D11	-9.4	-8.7	-8.1	-9.6	-9.6	-9.4
D12	-9.2	-8.5	-8.8	-9.9	-9.1	-8.5
D13	-9.3	-9.0	-8.5	-8.8	-9.2	-8.2
D14	-8.8	-8.5	-7.9	-9.0	-8.1	-7.5
D15	-9.4	-9.0	-8.2	-10	-9.1	-8.1
D16	9.0	-8.8	-8.1	-9.7	-9.1	-7.8

D17	-8.9	-8.6	-8.0	-9.3	-9.0	-8.3
D18	-9.0	-8.7	-8.0	-9.6	-9.6	-8.8
D19	-8.2	-8.4	-8.0	-9.3	-9.3	-8.0
D20	-8.7	-8.3	-7.8	-9.4	-8.2	-8.0
D21	-10.3	-8.4	-8.0	-9.7	-8.2	-8.8
D22	-9.2	-8.3	-8.1	-8.8	-7.6	-8.6
D23	-9.1	-8.2	-8.4	-9.7	-7.7	-7.8
D24	-8.9	-8.5	-8.2	-10.0	-9.6	-7.7
D25	-8.9	-8.9	-7.8	-9.7	-8.5	-7.8
D26	-9.1	-8.8	-7.7	-9.6	-9.6	-8.3
D27	-9.1	-8.9	-8.7	-9.8	-8.2	-8.3
D28	-8.9	-8.5	-8.2	-9.3	-9.7	-8.9
D29	-8.5	-8.9	-8.4	-9.8	-9.8	-7.5
D30	-8.7	-7.9	-8.1	-9.8	-9.6	-7.5
D31	-8.3	-8.9	-7.7	-10.1	-10.0	-7.5
D32	-9.0	-9.3	-9.0	-10.3	-10.4	-8.1
D33	-9.4	-8.6	-8.0	-9.3	-9.2	-8.6
D34	-8.7	-8.2	-8.1	-9.7	-9.6	-8.3
D35	-9.2	-8.6	-8.1	-10.3	-10.1	-7.4
D36	-9.0	-8.1	-8.3	-9.8	-9.7	-7.9
D37	-9.4	-8.8	-8.6	-10.2	-9.3	-8.0
D38	-9.1	-8.3	-8.1	-8.8	-9.3	-8.6
D39	-9.1	-8.6	-8.3	-10.4	-8.0	-9.1
D40	-8.6	-8.2	-7.9	-9.0	-8.4	-7.2
D41	-9.2	-9.0	-8.5	-8.6	-7.6	-7.9
D42	-9.0	-8.6	-8.3	-10.3	-9.6	-8.1
D43	-8.9	-8.2	-8.1	-9.6	-10.1	-8.8
D44	-9.8	-9.2	-8.7	-10.6	-10.3	-8.4
D45	-8.8	-8.2	-8.0	-9.7	-9.5	-7.9
D46	-9.0	-8.2	-8.0	-8.6	-8.3	-7.4
D47	-10.5	-9.4	-9.2	-10.0	-8.5	-8.5
D48	-8.0	-8.4	-7.7	-9.0	-7.9	-8.0
D49	-9.3	-8.3	-7.9	-8.8	-7.3	-7.7
D50	-8.8	-8.2	-8.2	-8.8	-8.9	-8.0
Rofecoxib	-8.1					
Omapatrilat		-9.6				
Lisinopril			-7.6			
Carazolol				-9.6		
losmapimod					-8.7	

Figure1: COX-2 receptor docked with D47

Figure 3: ACE receptor docked with D47

Figure 4: beta-1-adrenergic receptor docked with D10

Figure 5: MAPK receptor docked with D37

Figure 6: Neprilysin receptor docked with D11

Toxicity and ADMET prediction

The toxicity of compounds was evaluated using the Protox 3.0 software. The server admet generates pharmacokinetic characteristics of substances using various criteria: Absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion¹⁹. The results of admet analysis and toxicity prediction have been shown in table 4. Except for D1 (600 mg/kg), all examined compounds had greater LD50 values, indicating that they are non-toxic. Except for D6, D9, D27, D30, D33, D45, and D46, all of the chemicals chosen have no hepatotoxic properties. Except for D2, D3, D7, D21, D24, D32, D42, and D44, all of the derivatives have no

cardiotoxic activity. As a result, based on ADMET and toxicity analysis, some derivatives meet all of the mentioned requirements, and we may indicate that they are prospective candidates for the development of a better cardiovascular disease treatment.

Drug-likeness prediction

The Drug-likeness filters help in the early preclinical development by avoiding costly late step preclinical and clinical failure. The drug-likeness properties of molecules were analyzed based on Lipinski rule of 5 (Table 5). All the

selected compounds satisfied Lipinski's rule of five.

Table 4: ADMET prediction of selected derivatives used through swiss ADME and Protox-3.0 software

Compounds	LD50, (mg/kg)	Hepatotoxicity	Cardiotoxicity	Cytotoxicity	Carcinogens
D1	600 (class 4)	inactive	inactive	inactive	inactive
D2	4000 (class 5)	inactive	active	active	active
D3	2500 (class 5)	inactive	active	active	active
D4	4000 (class 5)	inactive	inactive	active	active
D5	2500 (class 5)	inactive	inactive	active	active
D6	2500 (class 5)	active	inactive	inactive	active
D7	2500 (class 5)	inactive	active	active	active
D8	4000 (class 5)	inactive	inactive	inactive	active
D9	2500 (class 5)	active	inactive	inactive	active
D10	2500 (class 5)	inactive	inactive	inactive	active
D11	2500 (class 5)	inactive	inactive	inactive	active
D12	2500 (class 5)	inactive	inactive	inactive	active
D13	2500 (class 5)	inactive	inactive	inactive	inactive
D14	4000 (class 5)	inactive	inactive	inactive	inactive
D15	2500 (class 5)	inactive	inactive	inactive	active
D16	2500 (class 5)	inactive	inactive	active	active
D17	4000 (class 5)	inactive	inactive	inactive	inactive
D18	2500 (class 5)	inactive	inactive	active	inactive
D19	2500 (class 5)	inactive	inactive	active	active
D20	2500 (class 5)	inactive	inactive	active	active
D21	2500 (class 5)	inactive	active	active	active

D22	4000 (class 5)	inactive	inactive	inactive	inactive
D23	4000 (class 5)	inactive	inactive	inactive	inactive
D24	4000 (class 5)	inactive	active	active	active
D25	2500 (class 5)	inactive	inactive	active	active
D26	2500 (class 5)	inactive	inactive	inactive	active
D27	2500 (class 5)	active	inactive	inactive	active
D28	4000 (class 5)	inactive	inactive	inactive	active
D29	2500 (class 5)	inactive	inactive	active	active
D30	2500 (class 5)	active	inactive	active	active
D31	2500 (class 5)	inactive	inactive	inactive	active
D32	2500 (class 5)	inactive	inactive	inactive	active
D33	2500 (class 5)	active	inactive	inactive	active
D34	2500 (class 5)	inactive	inactive	inactive	inactive
D35	4000 (class 5)	inactive	inactive	inactive	inactive
D36	4000 (class 5)	inactive	inactive	inactive	active
D37	4000 (class 5)	active	inactive	inactive	active
D38	4000 (class 5)	inactive	inactive	inactive	inactive
D39	4000 (class 5)	inactive	inactive	inactive	inactive
D40	4000 (class 5)	inactive	inactive	active	active
D41	2500 (class 5)	inactive	inactive	inactive	active
D42	4000 (class 5)	inactive	active	inactive	active
D43	2500 (class 5)	inactive	inactive	inactive	inactive
D44	4000 (class 5)	inactive	active	active	inactive
D45	4000 (class 5)	active	inactive	inactive	active

D46	2500 (class 5)	active	inactive	inactive	active
D47	2500 (class 5)	inactive	inactive	inactive	active
D48	2500 (class 5)	inactive	inactive	inactive	active
D49	4000 (class 5)	inactive	inactive	inactive	active
D50	2500 (class 5)	inactive	inactive	inactive	active

Table 5: Drug-likeness prediction of selected compounds.

	Molecular Formula	Molecular weight	Log p	TPSA	H-bond donar	H-bond accepter	Lipinski rule
D1	C ₁₅ H ₉ NO ₄	267.24 g/mol	2.56	76.03 Å ²	0	4	Yes
D2	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₃	238.24 g/mol	2.75	50.44 Å ²	1	3	Yes
D3	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₂	236.27 g/mol	3.50	30.21 Å ²	0	2	Yes
D4	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₃	252.26 g/mol	3.15	39.44 Å ²	0	3	Yes
D5	C ₁₅ H ₉ BrO ₂	301.13 g/mol	3.80	30.21 Å ²	0	1	Yes
D6	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ NO ₂	237.25 g/mol	2.61	56.23 Å ²	1	2	Yes
D7	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₃	238.24 g/mol	2.75	50.44 Å ²	1	3	Yes
D8	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₃	238.24 g/mol	2.78	50.44 Å ²	1	3	Yes
D9	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ NO ₂	237.25 g/mol	2.61	56.23 Å ²	1	2	Yes
D10	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₂	278.35 g/mol	4.38	30.21 Å ²	0	2	Yes
D11	C ₁₅ H ₉ BrO ₂	301.13 g/mol	3.80	30.21 Å ²	0	2	Yes
D12	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ O ₄	266.25 g/mol	2.64	67.51 Å ²	1	4	Yes
D13	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ O ₈	350.45 g/mol	4.19	50.44 Å ²	1	3	Yes
D14	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₅	312.32 g/mol	3.12	57.90 Å ²	0	5	Yes
D15	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₂	278.35 g/mol	4.38	30.21 Å ²	0	2	Yes
D16	C ₁₅ H ₉ ClO ₂	256.68 g/mol	3.71	30.21 Å ²	0	2	Yes
D17	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₄	282.29 g/mol	3.13	48.67 Å ²	0	4	Yes
D18	C ₁₅ H ₉ FO ₂	240.23 g/mol	3.48	30.21 Å ²	0	3	Yes
D19	C ₁₅ H ₉ FO ₂	240.23 g/mol	3.56	30.21 Å ²	0	3	Yes
D20	C ₁₅ H ₉ ClO ₂	256.68 g/mol	3.78	30.21 Å ²	0	2	Yes
D21	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₂	236.27 g/mol	3.51	30.21 Å ²	0	2	Yes
D22	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₆	328.32 g/mol	3.00	78.13 Å ²	1	6	Yes
D23	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₅	298.29 g/mol	2.95	68.90 Å ²	1	5	Yes
D24	C ₁₅ H ₉ ClO ₃	272.68 g/mol	3.59	50.44 Å ²	1	3	Yes
D25	C ₁₅ H ₉ IO ₂	348.14 g/mol	3.84	30.21 Å ²	0	2	Yes
D26	C ₁₅ H ₉ FO ₂	240.23 g/mol	3.49	30.21 Å ²	0	3	Yes
D27	C ₁₅ H ₉ NO ₄	267.24 g/mol	2.55	76.03 Å ²	0	4	Yes
D28	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₃	238.24 g/mol	2.78	50.44 Å ²	1	3	Yes
D29	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₂	236.27 g/mol	3.51	30.21 Å ²	0	2	Yes
D30	C ₁₅ H ₉ NO ₄	267.24 g/mol	2.54	76.03 Å ²	0	4	Yes
D31	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₂	250.29 g/mol	3.79	30.21 Å ²	0	2	Yes
D32	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₂	264.32 g/mol	4.11	30.21 Å ²	0	2	Yes
D33	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ NO ₂	237.25 g/mol	2.63	56.23 Å ²	1	2	Yes
D34	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₄	254.24 g/mol	2.64	70.67 Å ²	2	4	Yes
D35	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₃	252.26 g/mol	3.36	50.44 Å ²	1	3	Yes

D36	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₄	268.26 g/mol	3.04	59.67 Å ²	1	4	Yes
D37	C ₁₅ H ₉ NO ₅	283.24 g/mol	2.44	96.26 Å ²	1	5	Yes
D38	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₆	328.32 g/mol	3.00	78.13 Å ²	1	6	Yes
D39	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₃	266.29 g/mol	3.66	50.44 Å ²	1	3	Yes
D40	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ ClO ₃	286.71 g/mol	3.68	39.44 Å ²	0	3	Yes
D41	C ₁₅ H ₈ ClNO ₄	301.68 g/mol	3.07	76.03 Å ²	0	4	Yes
D42	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₃	252.26 g/mol	3.38	50.44 Å ²	1	3	Yes
D43	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₄	254.24 g/mol	2.67	70.67 Å ²	2	4	Yes
D44	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₃	280.32 g/mol	3.99	50.44 Å ²	1	3	Yes
D45	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ NO ₃	253.25 g/mol	2.50	76.46 Å ²	2	3	Yes
D46	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ ClNO ₂	271.70 g/mol	3.14	56.23 Å ²	1	2	Yes
D47	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ ClO ₂	298.76 g/mol	4.72	30.21 Å ²	0	2	Yes
D48	C ₁₅ H ₈ BrClO ₂	335.58 g/mol	4.39	30.21 Å ²	0	2	Yes
D49	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ ClO ₃	286.71 g/mol	3.76	39.44 Å ²	0	3	Yes
D50	C ₁₅ H ₈ Cl ₂ O ₂	291.13 g/mol	4.31	30.21 Å ²	0	2	Yes

DISCUSSION

In pharmaceutical research, computational strategies are of tremendous significance since they help in the identification and development of novel promising molecules, notably using molecular docking approaches^{20, 21}The angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) plays an important role in blood pressure regulation, and inhibiting ACE using inhibitory peptides is thought to be a main target for hypertension prevention. Several research employed the docking technique to block the expression of the ACE protein with drugs²². Among all derivatives, D10 (2-(4-tert-butylphenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one) has the lowest binding energy with β 1 adrenergic receptor (binding energy – 11.0 Kcal/mol), D47 with ACE and neutral endopeptidase inhibitors (binding energy – 9.4 Kcal/mol), D47 with ACE has lowest binding energy (binding energy – 9.2 Kcal/mol), for cox-2 the lowest binding energy with D47 derivative (binding energy – 10.5 Kcal/mol), D32 has lowest binding energy with receptor MAPK (binding energy – 10.4 Kcal/mol), D11 has lowest binding energy with protein neprilysin (binding energy – 9.4 Kcal/mol). In the present study, we have

selected 50 flavone derivatives which are synthesized from benzaldehyde and acetophenone derivatives against protein targets of various cardiovascular disease. It was found that among all selected above derivatives satisfy all parameters of ADMET and toxicity, also showed good affinity with selected protein targets, therefore, they could be used as potential broad -spectrum candidate for treatment of different heart problems.

CONCLUSIONS

The current study attempted to computationally find chemicals that can bind to the numerous targets of cardiovascular disease. The docking scores and interactions of the compounds indicate that the majority of the compounds can bind to several targets involved in cardiovascular disease. ADMET and toxicity prediction revealed that derivatives D10, D11, D32, and D47 could be employed as possible cardiovascular disease treatments.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Authors would like to acknowledge Priyadarshini JL College of Pharmacy, Nagpur, for providing research facilities

REFERENCES

1. Mc Namara K, Alzubaidi H, Jackson JK. Cardiovascular disease as a leading cause of death: how are pharmacists getting involved? *Integr Pharm Res Pract.* 2019;Volume 8:1-11. doi:10.2147/IPRP.S133088
2. Li X, Wu C, Lu J, et al. Cardiovascular risk factors in China: a nationwide population-based cohort study. *Lancet Public Health.* 2020;5(12):e672-e681. doi:10.1016/S2468-2667(20)30191-2
3. Nowbar AN, Gitto M, Howard JP, Francis DP, Al-Lamee R. Mortality From Ischemic Heart Disease: Analysis of Data From the World Health Organization and Coronary Artery Disease Risk Factors From NCD Risk Factor Collaboration. *Circ Cardiovasc Qual Outcomes.* 2019;12(6):e005375. doi:10.1161/CIRCOUTCOMES.118.005375
4. Abu Bakar NAF, Ahmad A, Wan Musa WZ, et al. Association between a dietary pattern high in saturated fatty acids, dietary energy density, and sodium with coronary heart disease. *Sci Rep.* 2022;12(1):13049. doi:10.1038/s41598-022-17388-5
5. Muzaffar R, Khan MA, Mushtaq MH, et al. Hyperhomocysteinemia as an Independent Risk Factor for Coronary Heart Disease. Comparison with Conventional Risk Factors. *Braz J Biol.* 2023;83:e249104. doi:10.1590/1519-6984.249104
6. Giannitsi S, Maria B, Bechlioulis A, Naka K. Endothelial dysfunction and heart failure: A review of the existing bibliography with emphasis on flow mediated dilation. *JRSM Cardiovasc Dis.* 2019;8:2048004019843047. doi:10.1177/2048004019843047
7. Venkatesan P, Maruthavanan T. Synthesis of substituted flavone derivatives as potent antimicrobial agents. *Bull Chem Soc Ethiop.* 2011;25(3). doi:10.4314/bcse.v25i3.68594
8. Lahyani A, Trabelsi M. Ultrasonic-assisted synthesis of flavones by oxidative cyclization of 2'-hydroxychalcones using iodine monochloride. *Ultrason Sonochem.* 2016;31:626-630. doi:10.1016/j.ultsonch.2016.02.018
9. Khan A, Jain A, Solank M. Synthesis and Biological Evaluation of Newly Synthesized Halogenated Flavones. *Orient J Chem.* 2024;40(2):562-568. doi:10.13005/ojc/400231
10. Totrov M, Abagyan R. Flexible ligand docking to multiple receptor conformations: a practical alternative. *Curr Opin Struct Biol.* 2008;18(2):178-184. doi:10.1016/j.sbi.2008.01.004
11. Shadidizaji A, Cinisli KT, Warda M, et al. In Silico Elucidation of the Binding Mechanisms and Molecular Dynamics of Oroxylin A -2,3-Dioxygenase Interaction: An Insight into Therapeutic Potentiation of Quercetin's Cardioprotection. *Recent Trends Pharmacol.* 2024;2(1):27-35. doi:10.62425/rtpharma.1455410
12. Alonso H, Bliznyuk AA, Gready JE. Combining docking and molecular dynamic simulations in drug design. *Med Res Rev.* 2006;26(5):531-568. doi:10.1002/med.20067
13. Morris GM, Huey R, Lindstrom W, et al. AutoDock4 and AutoDockTools4: Automated docking with selective receptor flexibility. *J Comput Chem.* 2009;30(16):2785-2791. doi:10.1002/jcc.21256
14. Cosconati S, Forli S, Perryman AL, Harris R, Goodsell DS, Olson AJ. Virtual screening with AutoDock: theory and practice. *Expert Opin Drug Discov.* 2010;5(6):597-607. doi:10.1517/17460441.2010.484460
15. Daina A, Michielin O, Zoete V. SwissADME: a free web tool to evaluate pharmacokinetics, drug-likeness and medicinal chemistry

- friendliness of small molecules. *Sci Rep.* 2017;7(1):42717. doi:10.1038/srep42717
16. Cheng F, Li W, Zhou Y, et al. admetSAR: A Comprehensive Source and Free Tool for Assessment of Chemical ADMET Properties. *J Chem Inf Model.* 2012;52(11):3099-3105. doi:10.1021/ci300367a
 17. Yang H, Lou C, Sun L, et al. admetSAR 2.0: web-service for prediction and optimization of chemical ADMET properties. Wren J, ed. *Bioinformatics.* 2019;35(6):1067-1069. doi:10.1093/bioinformatics/bty707
 18. Banerjee P, Eckert AO, Schrey AK, Preissner R. ProTox-II: a webserver for the prediction of toxicity of chemicals. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 2018;46(W1):W257-W263. doi:10.1093/nar/gky318
 19. Lounnas V, Ritschel T, Kelder J, McGuire R, Bywater RP, Foloppe N. CURRENT PROGRESS IN STRUCTURE-BASED RATIONAL DRUG DESIGN MARKS A NEW MINDSET IN DRUG DISCOVERY. *Comput Struct Biotechnol J.* 2013;5(6):e201302011. doi:10.5936/csbj.201302011
 20. Yuriev E, Ramsland PA (2013) Latest developments in molecular docking: 2010–2011 in review. *Journal of Molecular Recognition* 26: 215-239 doi: 10.1002/jmr.2266
 21. Ferreira LG, Dos Santos RN, Oliva G, Andricopulo AD (2015) Molecular docking and structure-based drug design strategies. *Molecules* 20: 13384-13421. doi: 10.3390/molecules200713384
 22. Tahir RA, Bashir A, Yousaf MN, Ahmed A, Dali Y, Khan S, Sehgal SA (2020). In Silico identification of angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitory peptides from MRJP1. *PloS one* 15:e0228265. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0228265

HOW TO CITE: Sneha Nandeshwar*, Sapan Shah, Rida Saiyad, Nikita Gaikwad, Pooja Wankhade, In-Silico Evaluation of Flavone Derivatives for Cardioprotective Effects: A Comparative Molecular Docking Approach, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 3, 2543-2556 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15087478>

